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RESULTS OF HUNTING THE RINGED PHEASANTS IN HUNTING GROUNDS OF AP VOJVODINA (SERBIA)*

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SUMMARY: Pheasant is the main game species in most of the Europe, therefore a large number of pheasant chicks is being artificially bred and released to hunting grounds every year in order to increase "natural population" and enable higher catch. This paper gives results of one-year investigation in hunting grounds of Autonomous Province of Vojvodina, showing that 19.67% (236) from total number of ringed and previously released pheasants (1200) was caught, so one of five released pheasant chicks were bagged. In hunting grounds Sonta, both ringed (170) and non-ringed (185) pheasants were released immediately before hunting. In total catch, there were 131 ringed ones (77.06%). Results of this investigation point that, regarding survival of artificially bred and released pheasants, they should be kept in shelters made according to regulated standards, with good conditions for pheasant game, and only after that they should be released into natural habitat; also the approach and the way of hunting this game should be modified.

Key words: pheasant, artificial breeding, catch percent

INTRODUCTION

The common pheasant (*Phasianus colchicus*) is naturally distributed from Caucasus Mountains, along the Black Sea, and to the east in Asia – in Korea, Manchuria, China, Japan and Formosa (Fuller and Garson, 2000). This natural range was widened due to its introduction in a much larger area. Mustin et al. (2011) notes introduction of this pheasant in almost fifty countries, and presently it is naturalized in most of the Europe and North America.

Pheasant is presently the main game species in most of the Europe, therefore a need has arisen to artificially breed large number of pheasant chicks which are released to hunting grounds every year in order to increase "natural population" and enable higher catch. During 1960's, when in Central, Eastern and South Europe number of

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partridges began to dwindle rapidly, a mass production of pheasants began with its organized release into hunting grounds. Since then, in larger European countries pheasant is the main game bird and this is the case in our country too. Such practice was continued until present days, although in our country number of pheasant released had been manifold decreased in last 15 years.

A number of studies that had been done did not establish a precise percent of catch for pheasants released in such a way, from artificial breeding centers with help of hunters-breeders (Klinger and Riegner, 2008). There are a relatively small number of studies that give details regarding weather conditions or causes of losses of released pheasants from artificial production and some studies point to the large losses due to intensive agricultural production using modern equipment and pesticides (Stoate, 2002).

Pheasant is the important factor in maintaining diversity in agricultural systems, mostly through planting, management and protection of forests (Nelli et al., 2012) and one of few game species which protection may be of financial importance.

The aim of these investigations is to, from data obtained and from literature data, find the percent of usage for seasonal populations, i.e. the populations where a significant number of pheasant chicks was released, and to establish effect of seasonal factors and ways of hunting on sustainability of this game species.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

These investigations were conducted during 2013 in five hunting grounds (Kovačica, Ada, Maradik, Rusko Selo, Sonta), with different habitat conditions and at different age of pheasant chicks. After the chicks were hatched and raised in pheasantries according to routine technology, at the age of 7-8 weeks they were ringed using plastic rings in different colors (depending on a hunters society) and transferred into enclosures. At the age of 12-13 weeks they were released into open hunting grounds (Kovačica, Ada, Maradik, Rusko Selo) and the first hunt was two months later (mid-October), with 9-12 hunting days per hunting grounds during 2013/14 hunting season, or were released immediately before every hunt (Sonta) with total of seven hunting days during pheasant hunting season.

After every hunt all pheasants caught were counted, males and females separately, and number of ringed individuals was noted. Thus obtained data were processed and shown in tables.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

During the hunting season, all ringed pheasants were noted and results of investigations regarding percent of bagged pheasants that were released into hunting grounds two months before the start of the hunting season are shown in Tables 1 and 2.

In four hunters' societies, with different biotopes, 1200 pheasant chicks aged 7-8 weeks were ringed in shelters. The ring color was coded for every hunting grounds in order to avoid errors in calculating hunting percent per hunting grounds. Number of hunt days in hunting grounds ranged between 9 and 12, and number of hunters and hunt method was differing significantly among hunting grounds. In Maradik and Rusko Selo hunting grounds hunt was organized every seven days as group hunt with battue. During the hunting season there was total of 54 hunt days, with 724 hunters participating.

Table 1. Results of hunting of pheasants that were released into hunting grounds two months before the hunting season

Hunting grounds	Number of hunt days	Number of hunters	Pheasants released (ringed)	Bagged, total	Bagged, ringed	% of ringed from total catch	% of ringed bagged, from total ringed released
Kovačica	12	63	200	28	19	67.86	9.50
Ada	9	80	200	77	37	48.05	18.50
Maradik	12	180	200	119	54	45.38	27.00
Rusko Selo	11	401	600	209	126	60.29	21.00
Total	54	724	1200	433	236	54.50	19.67

Table 2. Results of hunting pheasants that were released into hunting grounds two months before the hunting season, according to sex

Hunting grounds	Pheasants bagged			Number of ringed pheasants caught		
	Total	Males	Females	Total	Males	Females
Kovačica	28	19	9	19	14	5
Ada	77	54	23	37	28	9
Maradik	119	89	30	54	41	13
Rusko Selo	209	169	40	126	74	52
Total	433	331	102	236	157	79

From total of 433 pheasants bagged, there were 236 ringed ones, so share of ringed pheasants in total number of birds caught was 54.5%, and from total number of ringed pheasants released into hunting grounds 19.67% were caught. Real parameter of catch is 19.67%, pointing to conclusion that in such approach and technology for releasing pheasants into hunting grounds one of five released chicks was bagged.

Results of investigations by Gruychev (2014) point to a high percent of pheasant chicks losses in conditions of natural habitat (80%). The main causes for pheasant chick losses were carnivorous animals and human activities.

The similar issue was explored by Bagliacca et al. (2008) who examine the dispersion and habitat use after release of pheasants. They concluded that if pheasants are reared according to the disciplinary rules stated for the production of pheasants for wildlife reproduction programs, good survival rates and breeding succes of the released pheasants can be expected.

Present results from authors for hunting grounds in Vojvodina, with highly different percent of pheasants caught, may be explained by different habitat conditions and by omissions in sheltering. For instance, in hunters society in Mali Radinci 52% of released pheasant chicks were bagged and in hunting grounds of hunters' society Novi Sad it was under 10% (Ristić, 2005).

Based on investigations carried out in hunting grounds of Vojvodina regarding survival rate of artificially released pheasants (Ristić et al., 1995), it was established that percent of pheasants caught was ranging between 7.40% and 39.30% or 22.53% in average. From total number of branded pheasants (1720), 367 or 21.34% were caught, while in comparison to total caught (1575) percent of branded pheasants caught was 23.30%.

In our investigation, extremely low percent of caught pheasants (9.50%) was found in Kovačica hunting grounds, which may be explained by the fact that there was small number of hunters and hunt was organized near the settlements which limited free shooting. Better percent of pheasants bagged (60.29%) was in hunting grounds Rusko Selo, but their total number of hunters during pheasant hunting season (401) was considerably higher than in other hunters' societies.

Regarding results from the Sonta hunting grounds, data show that percent of ringed pheasants caught in comparison to those released immediately before hunt is much higher (Table 3).

Table 3. Results of hunting of ringed pheasants that were released immediately before hunt (hunting grounds Sonta)

	Released	Bagged	%
Non-ringed	185.00	125.00	67.57
Ringed	170.00	131.00	77.06
Total	355.00	256.00	72.11

Data from Table 3 show pheasant chicks released into hunting grounds immediately before each hunt, during the pheasant hunting season. There were seven hunts organized, with total of 170 ringed and 185 non-ringed pheasants released. Percent of caught ringed pheasants during the hunting season was 77.06%, which is rather high, but also a high percent of both ringed and non-ringed released pheasants was bagged (72.11%), and total number of bagged birds included also a number of previously existing pheasants from the same area, so this result is not quite exact.

Considering this issue, other authors also reached similar conclusions. FAWC (2008) emphasize importance of respecting all principles of breeding and releasing technology. In optimal environmental conditions and with good

care on pheasants, catch of 50% for released males may be attained. This is not the maximal result, since there are hunting grounds with catch higher than 60%, but the average value is about 35% from total number of chicks released. Losses in released pheasant chicks are difficult to estimate. As a rule, dead individuals are being noted only in immediate surroundings of the shelter, and even that is not thorough. According to the same authors, losses between release and hunt period may be about 30% from number of released pheasants, from which about 20% is caused by the habitat change (stress, diet disturbances etc) and 10% by predators.

Ristić (2005) noticed that it had been regarded as normal that 20 do 30% females are being caught. Where considerable decrease in number of pheasant game occurred, it is necessary to minimize number of females bagged in order to develop structure of basic flock and to locate it mostly in a center of the hunting grounds (at the circle of supposed dispersion of released birds), and at the same time to spare females at the edges since these are mostly populated by pheasants from existing local population.

By investigations of Ristić (2005) for 1973-2000 period in hunting grounds of Vojvodina about 5.4 million of pheasant chicks were released, mostly aged 5-6 or 7-8 weeks, with only about 10% of older categories (10, 12, 14 and 20 weeks, mature individuals and basic flock pheasants, so-called "old hens"). Most intensive period for introduction was from mid-seventies to beginning of 1990's. In 1973-2000 period, catch percent ranged from 10.54% minimum in 2000 to maximal 28.77% in 1973, with average catch of 22.02% for the entire period.

Based on investigations by Ristić (2006) percent of pheasant catch was 38.67% in hunting grounds "Rit" Beograd where immediate release method was used (during seven year period, 20,004 pheasants were released in mornings and 7,736 were bagged in the same day hunt). Using the same principle, in "Ristovača" hunting grounds result was 61.62% (for six year period, 25,175 pheasants were released in the mornings and 15,512 were bagged in the same day hunt).

CONCLUSION

From results obtained and their analysis, the following conclusions may be made:

Regarding survival of artificially bred, released and bagged pheasant chicks – they should be kept in shelters constructed according to regulation norms, with favorable conditions for pheasant game, since average catch percent in comparison to pheasant chicks released two months prior to hunt was 19.67%.

Pheasant should be hunted from the beginning of the hunting season, using group hunt with battue, and to let the grounds in peace at least seven days after every hunt.

Regarding ways of release, more appropriate are the hunting grounds with stable shelters: results are better with pheasant chicks between 5 and 6 weeks of age, while in hunting grounds with temporary shelters it is better to use 7-8 weeks old chicks.

In organizations where habitats have no perennial plants and the crops are harvested quickly, it is recommended to build enclosures in order to keep pheasants until the hunting season and to release birds into hunting grounds immediately before hunt. In such way losses are minimized, and catch percent is higher, in our case 77.06%.

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REZULTATI Odstrela prstenovanih fazana u lovištima AP VOJVODINE (SRBIJA)

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Izvod: Fazan je glavna vrsta lovne divljači u većem delu Evrope, što je dovelo do činjenice da se veliki broj fazančića veštački uzgaja i svake godine ispusti u lovišta, u pokušaju da se poveća "prirodna populacija" i mogućnost većeg izlova. U ovom radu su izneti rezultati jednogodišnjeg istraživanja u lovištima AP Vojvodine, koji ukazuju da je izlovljeno 19,66% (236) u odnosu na ukupan broj prstenovanih i prethodno puštenih fazana (1.200), što znači da je odstreljeno svako peto fazansko pile koje je ispušteno u lovište. U lovištu Sonta puštani su "pred pušku" i prstenovani (170) i neprstenovani fazani (185). Ukupno je odstreljeno 131 prstenovanih fazana što iznosi 76,47%. Rezultati ovog istraživanja ukazuju da kada je u pitanju preživljavanje veštački proizvedenih i unetih fazančića – iste treba čuvati u prihvatilištima koja su napravljena po propisanim normama, i u kojima su stvoreni dobri uslovi za fazansku divljač, tek onda ispuštati u prirodni ambijent, ali isto tako i promeniti pristup u načinu lova ove divljači.

Ključne reči: fazan, veštačka proizvodnja, procenat odstrela.

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